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D6.1 Collaboration plan with definition of common objectives and activities including milestones

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EuroHPC
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Executive Summary

This deliverable aims to present the Plasma-PEPSC collaboration plan with associated milestones, the initial dissemination, training, and exploitation plans for the project. We also report on the project communication channels and the dissemination activities in the first six months of the project.

In particular, we present the following:

- The collaboration objectives, plan, and activities with the CASTIEL-2 and other CoEs.
- The Plasma-PEPSC dissemination and training plan, including the communication strategy, target groups, and key performance indicators.
- The two channels of Plasma-PEPSC were established during the first six months of the Plasma-PEPSC project, such as the website and Twitter.
- The exploitation plan, including standardization efforts in Plasma-PEPSC.

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1 Introduction

Collaboration with other CASTIEL 2, EuroHPC projects, and Centers of Excellence (CoE), communication, dissemination, and exploitation of the results achieved in Plasma-PEPSC are one of the Plasma-PEPSC key objectives. Only through these activities, Plasma-PEPSC can impact the European and global HPC and plasma research and industry communities and beyond. The basis for all actions will be a comprehensive and concerted collaboration, dissemination, training, and exploitation campaign.

All the measures, approaches, and goals set out in this document may accordingly be subject to change over the lifetime of the project, which cannot be foreseen at this point in time.

The remainder of this document is structured as follows:

- Section 2 presents the collaboration objectives, plan, and associated milestones as coordinated by the CASTIEL 2 project.
- Section 3 presents the dissemination plan and activities with the associated target audience and key performance indicators. We also report on the first six months of Plasma-PEPSC dissemination activities.
- Section 4 presents the communication channels that are already set up: the Plasma-PEPSC webpage and Twitter page.
- Section 5 describes the exploitation plan and standardization activities
- Section 6 concludes the deliverable.

2 Collaboration Objectives & Plan

This section describes the initial collaboration objectives on critical aspects of the projects (collaboration on software engineering, access to EuroHPC systems, coordinated dissemination and exploitation) as presented in CASTIEL 2 Deliverable D1.7 [1].

2.1 Collaboration Objectives

The EuroHPC CASTIEL 2 (Coordination & Support for National Competence Centres on a European Level Phase 2) project identifies a number of collaboration objectives to achieve with Plasma-PEPSC [1]. We report them below.

Legacy Codes & Porting to EuroHPC System. Plasma-PEPSC, with the collaboration and coordination of CASTIEL 2, will:

- Identify required software re-engineering in the four Plasma-PEPSC software codes (BIT, GENE, PIconGPU, and Vlasiator) to facilitate migration and maintenance on JU supercomputers (both current and future)
- Identify requirements in terms of personnel resources and time scales and suggestions for actions to meet those requirements.

Continuous Integration & Continuous Deployment Platform. One of Plasma-PEPSC's objectives is to ease the deployment of the four applications onto EuroHPC supercomputers following the coordinated direction of CASTIEL 2. To lower this hurdle and enable code owners and end users to deploy with minimal overhead on multiple supercomputers, CASTIEL 2 coordinates the implementation of a common continuous integration and deployment platform across all EuroHPC supercomputers.

In the first phase, Plasma-PEPSC deploys the four codes available on EuroHPC supercomputers, ideally with minimal or no code changes.

To foster the implementation of such an integration platform, CASTIEL 2 coordinates this activity while bringing together representatives from all current and future EuroHPC supercomputing sites and CoEs. CASTIEL 2 has set up early on a mailing list to facilitate discussions between all stakeholders and organizes monthly conference calls to guide the integration process and provide an open space for discussion.

Currently, the Jacamar Continuous Integration (CI) framework project is proposed to ensure a minimally invasive setup for both the hosting sites and the CoEs. Since most EuroHPC supercomputing sites operate some CI/CD environment (not necessarily Jacamar CI), CASTIEL 2 will match Plasma-PEPSC with a hosting site to gain the first hands-on experience.

Based on the lessons learned and additional requirements that Plasma-PEPSC codes might impose, CASTIEL 2 will develop the final CI/CD concept to be implemented across all EuroHPC supercomputing sites in close collaboration with all stakeholders.

Special Access Scheme to EuroHPC Systems. CASTIEL 2 will support Plasma-PESC in achieving appropriate resource access to the EuroHPC supercomputers to enable us to reach their objectives for deployment and delivery of application software on those systems. To ensure the timely initiation of the CoE activities on the EuroHPC JU systems, CASTIEL 2 proposed two initial access models:

1. A *flat-rate* or *base-rate* approach for benchmark and development-type access. This approach assigns a fixed number of resources to each code. It includes access to all systems for benchmarking purposes and selected systems for development.
2. An individualized yet accelerated approach for regular and high-priority access.

2.2 Collaboration Activities

Together and under the coordination of CASTIEL 2, Plasma-PEPSC collaboration activities will be:

- **Collaboration between CoEs and NCCs.** As a first step, CASTIEL 2 supports the operation of a communication channel between all CoEs (the HPC CoE Council). These communication channels will then facilitate regular discussions between NCCs and CoEs on topics of mutual interest to enable initiatives and working groups.
- **Enabling Exchange of Expertise.** This activity supports the exchange of training-related best practices, available resources, knowledge, and information within and between NCCs and CoEs. This will also ease any co-design activities planned by CoEs.
- **Fostering Industrial Interaction.** This activity aims to identify and implement actions and to increase Plasma-PEPSC outreach to the industry through sectorial events, industry bodies, or industry-specific communication channels.
- **Collaboration in Training.** This activity aims to facilitate access to training offered at the national and European levels to interested NCCs and other potential users (from industry, academia, or the public sector). This task will also establish effective cooperation and leverage synergies with other European initiatives around training in HPC, including *EUMaster4HPC* and *ETP4HPC*, among others.

2.3 Collaboration with SPACE EuroHPC Center of Excellence

In the first six months of the project, we engaged with the SPACE EuroHPC CoE, which also focuses on plasma simulation codes, specifically for space and astrophysical applications. We collaborated with the EuroHPC on preparing a joint poster for the ISC2023 EuroHPC booth, see Figure 1. Together with SPACE, we are working on a proposal for a joint workshop at HiPEAC Conference 2024.

Figure 1 - Joint Poster at the ISC2023 EuroHPC booth.

2.4 Associated Milestones

Two milestones associated with the collaboration plan with CASTIEL 2 have been set:

- MS5 - *Access to European and worldwide systems secured, including EuroHPC pilots and pre-exascale systems* – Due date: 31-Dec-23
- MS21 - *Collaboration agreement has been signed*. Due Date: 30-Jun-23. The coordination and leadership for preparing the collaboration agreement is taken by CASTIEL 2.

3 Dissemination & Training

The project's dissemination activities aim to maximize its impact and widely disseminate its results. Depending on the target audience (general public, decision-makers, plasma communities in academia and industry, HPC communities in industry and academia), different measures will be defined with clear impact and KPIs. Our dissemination activities have different aims:

- **Awareness creation:** awareness in the general public and with decision-makers needs to be created on the importance of the project presenting its important social impact (fusion energy, accelerators for hospitals and chip manufacturing, space weather), and its goals.
- **Promotion of software:** further uptake of the software targeted by the project can be achieved through specialized dissemination activities with possible user communities in academia and industry, including the Competence Centres.
- **Promotion of HPC & EuroHPC:** the use of HPC, and EuroHPC in particular, needs to be promoted in the wider plasma communities in research and industry; here, collaboration with the Competence Centres will play an important role.
- **Knowledge transfer:** the knowledge developed in the project needs to be transferred, creating a vibrant community of HPC technology developers and users in the plasma domain.

Plasma-PEPSC will also work on **training activities** in collaboration with CASTIEL 2. To support early engagement in the plasma physics simulation community (fusion, industrial plasmas, accelerator physics, space physics, and astrophysics), Plasma-PEPSC will organize a training facility with remote access to enlarge user access across the whole community. This facility aims at easy integration into other training courses on plasma physics and high-performance computing. This task will establish professional links with academic staff at universities across Europe for future cooperation and familiarise undergraduate and graduate participants with local and European training opportunities and grant schemes for young researchers. Furthermore, this task will take responsibility for organizing events, e.g., webinars and a summer school to facilitate early dissemination of outcomes to early-career scientists in the space of plasma simulation techniques, comprising aspects of HPC developments. Content of these events will subsequently be included in the graduate and undergraduate studies at the academic partners.

3.1 Dissemination & Training Activities

Specific dissemination activities initially planned, together with the target audience and KPIs, are summarised in the table below.

Dissemination Activity	Dissemination Target	Key Performance Indicators
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Website and social media	Society, Industry, Scientific and HPC Communities	Website is updated monthly and receives at least 100 unique visits per month. At least three Twitter posts per month.
Press releases	Industry, Scientific and HPC Communities	At least three press releases by the end of the project: one at the beginning of the project, and two after the software releases cycles (M24 and M48).
Webinars	Industry, Scientific and HPC Communities	At least four webinars with more than 25 participants by M48.
Open-source software	Industry, Scientific and HPC Communities	Plasma-PEPSC software is available/readily installable on all EuroHPC systems.
Open-access publications	Industry, Scientific and HPC Communities	At least five papers per year are published on the results of the Plasma-PEPSC project in conference proceedings and scientific journals.
Conference and workshops	HPC and computational plasma physics professionals, graduate and post-graduate researchers	At least five participations in conferences or workshops, presenting the Plasma-PEPSC results. At least one workshop organised by the end of the project.
Collaboration with other EuroHPC CoEs and Competence Centers	EuroHPC CoE members and EuroHPC national competence centres	At least one joint event (conference, workshop, article preparation, winter/summer school) with at least one CoE and a competence centre.
Collaboration with EPI	EPI Research and Industry	At least one research meeting with EPI representatives to present current results and feedback on the co-design with the European processor and accelerator.
Community building	Computational Plasma Physics Community, Applied Plasma Physics	At least two Birds-of-a-Feather (BOF) events at SC or ISC on the plasma simulation community building by the end of the project.
Training and Education	HPC and computational plasma physics professionals, graduate, and post-graduate researchers	At least one summer school on plasma simulation techniques and HPC organised or co-organised by the Plasma-PEPSC consortium by the end of the project.

Standardization	Standardisation committees and MPI & OpenMP communities	Attendance at four committee meetings providing input from Plasma-PEPSC experiences, where applicable.
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3.2 Dissemination via Publications

One of the major dissemination channels targeting the exascale community is the publication of scientific articles in journals, conferences, and workshop proceedings. For the publication of our work, we will target high-profile conferences for computational plasma physicists (ICNSP, EPS, APS, EGU, AGU) and journals (Physics of Plasmas, Plasma Physics and Controlled Fusion, JGR, GRL, Journal of Computational Physics, Computer Physics Communications).

Plasma-PEPSC will seek contributions to HPC conferences that include an applications track, such as Supercomputing, ISC, IPDPS, HPDC, Cluster, EuroPar, CCGrid, PASC among the others, and journals, such as International Journal of High-Performance Computing Applications, Journal of Supercomputing, Journal of Parallel and Distributed Computing, and Concurrency and Computation: Practice and Experience, Transactions on Parallel and Distributed Systems.

All the publications will be available as green open access, allowing for major dissemination of the scientific outcomes of the project.

3.3 Dissemination Activities in the First Six Months

During the first six months, the Plasma-PEPSC project members have been involved in a series of dissemination activities:

- Presentations and poster at the EuroHPC Summit 2023 in Göteborg, Sweden, 20-23 March, 2023. See Figures 2-4.
- Plasma-PEPSC presentation at the ISC 2023 EuroHPC Booth, at ISC2023, Hamburg, Germany. May 13, 2023. Attendees: 20. See Figures 4-5
- Organization of the ISC Birds of Feather (BoF) at ISC2023, Hamburg, Germany. Attendees: 35. May 14, 2024. See Figures 6 and 7.
- Part of the organizers of the PASC 2023 mini-symposium “Exascale Plasma Simulations, Methods and Technologies for Fusion, Plasma Accelerator and Space Physics Research” on June 26-28, 2023. Organizer(s): Stefano Markidis, Jeremy Williams, Michael Bussmann, Sriramkrishnan Muralikrishnan and Andreas Adelman. See Figures 8 and 9 for two presentations from the Plasma-PEPSC project at PASC 2023.
- A presentation about Plasma-PEPSC at HPC Workshops on June 30, Cetraro, Italy.

Figure 2 – Markidis’ presentation at the EuroHPC Summit on the challenges and gaps for plasma simulations.

Figure 3 - Jeremy Williams discussed Plasma-PEPSC at the EuroHPC summit workshop.

Figure 4 - Plasma-PEPSC Presentation at the EuroHPC Summit 2023.

Figure 5 - Plasma-PEPSC Presentation at the ISC2023 EuroHPC Booth.

Figure 6 - Plasma-PEPSC presentation at the EuroHPC project.

Figure 7 - Plasma-PESC Birds of Feather at ISC2023 and presentation of the working group results by Erwin Laure (MPG), Filippo Mantovani (BSC), and Markus Battarbee (UoH).

Figure 8 - Presentation by David Tskhakaya about BIT at PASC2023

Figure 9 - Presentation by Frank Jenko (MPG) about GENE and GENE-X at PASC2023

4 Plasma-PEPSC Communication Channels

Media channels play a major role in the communication strategy. We will focus on digital channels: the website and social media.

4.1 Website

The project's website is the central content hub for Plasma-PEPSC. The website is well-established, with a high visit rate. Most content will be published here first and will then be pushed into the social media channels. Shorter content snippets with only short-term relevance will be published on social media only to keep the website as straightforward as possible. Figures 8-9 shows a few snapshots of the Plasma-PEPSC object.

The website has been set up since the project kicked off, and it grew over time to maintain a general update following these three principles:

- **Accessible:** Structure and content should be delivered in a way that allows access for everybody from any device with no special requirements. That includes a very clean and simple appearance and accessibility for people with disabilities.
- **Scalable:** The website must be able to scale and grow further with the proceeding of the project. Also, it must be able to adapt to new trends in dissemination as they emerge.
- **Maintainable:** The website must be easy to maintain and support. Therefore, the Content Management System (CMS) and theme should be customized as little as possible. It also should allow for gathering the number of visitor information.

Figure 10 - Plasma-PEPSC WEB landing page.

Figure 11 - The Plasma-PEPSC webpage includes videos and material about the four Plasma-PEPC codes.

Figure 12 - The Plasma-PEPSC CMS allows us to follow the number of website visitors.

4.2 Twitter

Existing social media channels will be used further. As of now, Twitter (see a snapshot of the Plasma-PEPSC Twitter Webpage below) has shown to be very efficient in addressing the target audiences in academia and industry. In general, social media has shown to be very dynamic in terms of platforms and audiences. To broaden the reach of Plasma-PEPSC, additional social media channels, such as LinkedIn, are considered.

The image shows a screenshot of the Twitter profile for Plasma-PEPSC. The browser address bar at the top shows 'twitter.com/Plasma_PEPSC_EU'. The profile header includes the name 'Plasma-PEPSC - EuroHPC CoE for Plasma Si...' and the handle '@Plasma_PEPSC_EU'. The bio states 'Plasma-PEPSC - EuroHPC CoE for Plasma Simulations' and provides the website 'plasma-pepsc.eu' and the date 'Joined January 2023'. The profile shows 12 following and 13 followers. The main content area features a large group photo of team members in front of a presentation screen. To the right, there is a 'You might like' section with recommendations for 'EUPEX Pilot' and 'EuroCC@Belgium'. The left sidebar contains navigation options: Home, Explore, Notifications, Messages, Lists, Bookmarks, and Verified.

Figure 13 - Plasma-PEPSC Twitter page

5 Exploitation Plan

To ensure the adoption and exploitation of the results within the computational plasma physics and HPC communities, the Plasma-PEPSC project members are committed to open standard, open interface, and open-source software up to the limits described in the next section.

In Plasma-PEPSC, we aim to optimize, scale, and develop applications with worldwide usage and adoption. In doing this, the project will create a number of exploitable results:

1. Plasma simulation software running efficiently on (pre-)exascale systems.
2. Input to the European processor and accelerator developments.
3. Publications on best practices and novel methods to deal with extreme parallelism, accelerators, and extreme data.
4. Training and education material in plasma simulation tools, HPC, and tools for extreme-scale data analytics.

Specific exploitation activities for these results include:

- We will facilitate the adoption and exploitation of the results of the Plasma-PEPSC project by releasing versions of the four plasma simulation codes (BIT, GENE, PIconGPU, and Vlasiator). The optimized software will be open and free to use for any interested user. We will make available analysis tools and datasets relevant to the proposal's grand scientific challenges.
- A dedicated part of the Plasma-PEPSC website will be implemented. The plasma simulation codes will be described in detail to foster further developments by the interested scientific community.
- All the publications produced by the Plasma-PEPSC will be open-access and archived in open-access repositories, such as *arxiv.org*.
- We will promote the design and development of the European processor and accelerator through co-design activities.
- The results from the Plasma-PEPSC project will also be used by the academic parties in research and teaching in graduate classes in computational physics, computational electromagnetics, plasma physics, space physics, space weather, and HPC courses.

5.1 Exploitation by Plasma-PEPSC Partners

All the code owners (IPP CAS with BIT, MPG with GENE, HZDR with PIconGPU, and UoH with Vlasiator) will exploit the major Plasma-PEPSC advancements in performance and portability for increased adoption in the community and liaisons with European agencies, initiatives (EURATOM, EuroFusion, and ESA), projects and the national and international research communities.

SIPEARL is the main Plasma-PEPSC industrial partner. SIPEARL is considered by many at the European level as the cornerstone of the EU strategy toward improved autonomy and sovereignty in High-Performance Computing. This requires that EU HPC

ecosystem, all of IPR, HW, and SW, including benchmarking and application performance, work with SIPEARL processors in close connection with the best-in-class accelerators available in the project timeframe. Plasma-PEPSC will provide feedback to EPI's RISC-V developments, test it on real Plasma-PEPSC kernels and start preparing future IPRs based on RISC-V that are needed for developing an efficient and competitive European accelerator.

All academic partners (KTH, TUM, UoH, UL) will perform exploitation in the direction of academia (seminars and courses based on their work), research projects (expanding their network between the industry and academia in Europe), research contracts (transfer of technology to European industry and SMEs) and contribution to standardization bodies (MPI).

All HPC and Research Centres (MPG, BSC, FORTH, HZDR, IPP CAS) will plan to address the plasma simulation optimizations that are of high importance for them in terms of HPC system users. The expected scientific publications resulting from their research will further contribute to their academic reputation and facilitate new cooperation. All HPC centers have a training strategy towards the European research community as an outcome of their work, also fostering and promoting the uptake of the Plasma-PEPSC simulation codes.

5.2 MPI and OpenMP Standardisation Efforts

The co-design activities of Plasma-PEPSC will directly contribute to standardization activities, particularly for MPI and OpenMP. Use cases and applications concerning MPI-related requirements and potential new extensions will be published to the MPI community and, if appropriate, introduced to the MPI Forum for possible standardization. Modern concepts in MPI and upcoming proposals are critical for enabling high-performance application implementations for Plasma-PEPSC developments, including load-balancing, resilience, and support for accelerators on extreme-scale systems. The PI at TUM, Martin Schulz, is also currently leading the MPI Forum, the standardization body for the Message Passing Interface (MPI) and TUM will be the bridge between Plasma-PEPSC and the MPI Forum.

BSC and TUM also are involved in the OpenMP standardization effort and will provide a link between the CoE and the OpenMP community. BSC is part of the Architecture Review Board (ARB) of OpenMP and Language committees and has actively pushed and developed new features into the standard.

6 Conclusion

This deliverable lays out the planned collaboration, communication, exploitation objectives, plans, activities, and associated project milestones and key performance indicators. We reported about the dissemination in the first six months. And presented channels for maximizing the impact and broadcasting the outcomes of the project. As an initial plan, these approaches will continue to be adapted and improved to changing trends in communication and new requirements.

References

[1] CASTIEL 2, *D1.7 Collaboration Plan with the CoEs*, Miriam Koch, Jisika Yono, Dennis Hoppe, Guy Lonsdale, Guntram Berti.